

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF ELASTIC-PLASTIC BEHAVIOUR COUPLED WITH DAMAGE IN METAL/COMPOSITE LAMINATES. APPLICATION TO ARALL AND GLARE MATERIALS.

A. HUREZ*, J.M. ROELANDT*, A. ABISROR**

* Laboratoire de Génie Mécanique pour les Matériaux et les Structures
Dépt de Génie Mécanique - Division Modèles Numériques en Mécanique
BP 649 - 60206 Compiègne Cédex - France

** Aérospatiale - Centre Commun de Recherches Louis Blériot
12, rue Pasteur - BP 76 - 92152 Suresnes - France

ABSTRACT

A non-linear numerical method is presented to calculate laminates made of metallic and composite layers (ARALL type). We use a Q4 γ membrane-bending finite element including transverse shear effects. The constitutive relation for a layer is either isotropic elastic-plastic (metal) or transversely isotropic with damage (composite). We use a coupled damage behaviour, based on Ladeveze et al. approach, which associates the composite deterioration to fibre-matrix decohesion and to matrix cracking. The identification of the constitutive relations has been carried out with tension tests on material components. Experimental tests show a good agreement with numerical results.

Keywords : modelling, plate element, damage, ARALL, GLARE

INTRODUCTION

The application of composite materials to transport aircraft structures such as empennages and the moving surfaces of wings has been one of the major aeronautical advances of the last decade. Today, composite wing box structures are under development at most aerospace companies. For example, the composite content in the latest transport aircraft represents approximately 15 % of the total structural mass.

During the last ten years, the potential application of fibre metal laminates for fuselages has been investigated in Europe and USA. For example, ARALL (Aramid Reinforced ALuminium Laminates) and GLARE (GLass REinforced aluminium laminates) consist of thin aluminium sheets bonded by adhesive impregnated with Kevlar (respectively Glass) fibres. The most commonly produced lay up sequences are 1mm to 2 mm thick. The progress made by the collaborative workers has underlined the potential of fibre metal laminate fuselage applications being realisable. The anticipated weight saving potential is thought to be roughly comparable to that which may be possible through the use of carbon fibre reinforced plastic technology.

Moreover, the nature of the problems to be addressed with the latter materials are significantly more complex : low allowable strains, susceptibility to impact damage, damage tolerance aspects.

We present a non-linear method to calculate laminates with metallic layers or long fibre reinforced composites of ARALL type.

We use a Q4 γ membrane-bending finite element including transverse shear effects. The constitutive relation for a layer is either isotropic elastic-plastic (metal) or transversely isotropic with damage (composite). We use a coupled damage behaviour, based on Ladeveze et al. approach, which associates the composite deterioration to fibre-matrix decohesion and to matrix cracking. We have applied this method to study the behaviour of ARALL and GLARE laminates.

1. LAMINATES UNDER STUDY

ARALL (Aramid Reinforced ALuminium Laminates) has been developed in the 1970s by Delft University and Fokker Company. They found that fracture toughness increased and fatigue crack growth was limited when thinner metal was used in bounded structures [1].

The incorporation of fibres in the bound layer improved these properties further still. This work led Fokker to the development of hybrid laminates / ARALL and GLARE (GLASS REinforced aluminium laminates). They consist of a lay up of unidirectional (or crossed - 0 / 90) composite layers (aramid-epoxy for ARALL, glass-epoxy for GLARE). These laminates are available from 2/1 (2 layers of aluminium alloy 1 layer of composite) to 5/4 (figure 1). The thickness of the aluminium and composite layers is respectively about 0.3 mm and 0.25 mm.

These materials have excellent fatigue properties due to unbroken composite fibres bridging the crack edges.

Fig. 1 : ARALL or GLARE materials (3 / 2)

2. THE Q4 γ FINITE ELEMENT

Considering the thicknesses of ARALL and GLARE materials, we have chosen plate elements with small strains.

The finite element we used has been described and tested by many authors, especially by S.W. BATHE [2]. This element is based on the Mindlin-Reissner theory of plates. It is a four-nodes quadrilateral element, including transverse shear effects. The approximation is bilinear for the geometry and the displacements u , v , w , β_x , β_y . On the other hand, transverse shear strains have a special approximation scheme. For this element, the shear correction factors are determined by an energy method proposed by J.L. BATOZ and G.DHATT [3].

3. THE CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

Experimental results have shown that ARALL and GLARE materials may be modelled by using an elastic-plastic behaviour coupled with damage. This model can take into account the observed phenomena except the following : viscous behaviour of the composite layers and damage of aluminium alloy, which are neglected in comparison with other phenomena. In order to simplify the model, we neglect the plasticity of the resin, even though it seems to be relatively important.

The aluminium alloy layers are assumed to be elastic-plastic with strain hardening (isotropic or kinematical hardening), their fracture is considered to be sudden, happening for a critical value of strain (no progressive damage). Composite layers are supposed to be elastic with damage. The involved progressive damage represents fibre-matrix decohesion and matrix cracking.

3.1. Plasticity

The behaviour of aluminium alloy layers is elastic-plastic.

Plasticity threshold is given by : $\Phi = \frac{1}{3} (J_2)^2 - \frac{1}{3} k(p)^2$

where J_2 is the equivalent Von Mises stress and $k(p)$ the updated yield stress (taking into account isotropic strain hardening).

3.2. Damage

Damage mechanics theory has been introduced by L.M. KATCHANOV et Y.N. RABOTNOV : variations in the elastic characteristics of a material are indicators of its deterioration. Damage mechanics based on effective stress has been developed in France principally by J. LEMAITRE et J.L. CHABOCHE for metallic materials and by P. LADEVEZE et al. [4], [5], [6] for composite materials. P. LADEVEZE et al. [4] propose a ply-scale approach, the composite ply being considered homogeneous. We use this type of model in our work. The damaged material strain energy is :

$$E_D = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sigma_1^2}{E_1^0} - 2 \frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \frac{(\sigma_2)^2}{E_2^0 (1-d')} + \frac{(\sigma_2)^2}{E_2^0} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{G_{12}^0 (1-d)} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{G_{12}^0 (1-d)} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{G_{23}^0} \right]$$

Transverse shear stresses σ_{13} and σ_{23} are small with respect to other stresses. This is the reason for taking into account the damage linked to 1-3 shear stress (transverse isotropy hypothesis). In this method we use two damage variables d and d' acting upon shear modulus G_{12} and transverse modulus E_2 provided that σ_2 is a tension stress (otherwise d' does not change, transverse cracks being closed under compression).

$$G_{12} = G_{12}^0 (1-d) \quad E_2 = E_2^0 (1-d')$$

The variables associated with damage are :

$$Y_d = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{G_{12}^0 (1-d)^2} \quad Y_{d'} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\sigma_2)^2}{E_2^0 (1-d')^2}$$

The no-damage threshold for the elementary layer is given by :

$$Y(t) = \sup_{\tau \leq t} \left(\sqrt{Y_d(\tau) + b Y_{d'}(\tau)} \right)$$

$$Y'(t) = \sup_{\tau \leq t} \left(\sqrt{Y_{d'}(\tau)} \right)$$

The evolution laws for d and d' are associated to fibre-matrix decohesion and to matrix cracking.

$$d = \frac{\langle Y - Y_0 \rangle_+}{Y_c} \quad \text{si } d < 1 \quad \text{et } Y' < Y'_s \quad \text{et } Y < Y_R \quad \text{sinon } d = 1$$

$$d' = \frac{\langle Y - Y'_0 \rangle_+}{Y'_c} \quad \text{si } d' < 1 \quad \text{et } Y' < Y'_s \quad \text{et } Y < Y_R \quad \text{sinon } d' = 1$$

The parameters Y_0 , Y_c , Y'_0 , Y'_c , b et Y'_s are determined experimentally. Their identification is achieved by means of tension tests and a few loading-unloading cycles on four stacking sequences ([0]₈, [± 45]_{2S}, [45]₈, [± 67.5]_{2S}). For cycle i , damage is characterised by the decrease of material stiffness :

$$d_i = 1 - \frac{E^i}{E^0}$$

Fig 2 : $\underline{Y} = f(d)$ curve for verre-epoxy

Fig 3 : $\underline{Y} = f(d')$ curve for verre-epoxy

Material constants for 2024T3 aluminium alloy :

Young modulus $E = 69500 \pm 6600$ MPa, Poisson ratio $\nu = 0,33 \pm 0,06$

stress-strain law $\sigma = C (p + p_0)^\alpha$

$C = 512 \pm 15$ MPa, $\alpha = 0,066 \pm 0,004$, $\sigma_y = 310 \pm 30$ MPa for $p_0 = 0,05$ %

Material constants for glass-epoxy composite (axis 1 is fibres axis) :

modulus $E_1 = 61900 \pm 2500$ MPa, $E_2 = 8500 \pm 1000$ MPa

Poisson ratio $\nu_{12} = 0,28 \pm 0,02$

shear moduli $G_{12} = G_{23} = 3250 \pm 200$ MPa

damage constants

$Y_c = 2,0 \pm 0,3 \sqrt{\text{MPa}}$, $Y_0 = 0,12 \pm 0,04 \sqrt{\text{MPa}}$,

$Y'_c = 2,3 \pm 0,6 \sqrt{\text{MPa}}$, $Y'_0 = 0,00 \pm 0,15 \sqrt{\text{MPa}}$

coupling parameter between Y_d and $Y_{d'}$: $b = 3,4 \pm 0,6$

critical values : $\epsilon_{1R} \approx 3,5$ %, $Y_s \approx 1,1 \sqrt{\text{MPa}}$, $Y_R \approx 2 \sqrt{\text{MPa}}$

3.3 Numerical algorithm

We use a Newton-Raphson iterative scheme. Constitutive relations for plasticity and damage are written under an implicit form [7].

The elementary tangent stiffness matrices and residues integration needs a 2×2 Gauss points in the mid-plane and 3 points in each layer thickness. Numerical integration through the thickness is necessary because of plasticity or damage state at different locations in the same layer.

Shear correction factors calculation leads to the use of three Gauss points in each layer thickness.

4. RESULTS

The calculations that we have carried out simulate experimental tests on GLARE2 (2024T3 alloy-unidirectional glass-epoxy) under tension or bending.

4.1. Tension tests

Fig. 4: Results for tension on GLARE 2 (10°)

Fig. 5 : Results for tension on GLARE 2 (45°)

Experimental and numerical results are very close. Stress-strain curves are well represented by the numerical model.

However, we can notice a drop of stress in the nonlinear part of calculated curve for 45° orientation. This represents the breaking of glass-epoxy plies, as it can be seen for damage evolution.

Actually, this breaking is less sudden. The resin plasticity, which is not taken into account, would smooth the resulting curve.

Damage evolution depends on the orientation of loading with respect to fibres.

We also show on these curves numerical results for which :

- composite layers are elastic without damage.
- composite layers are totally broken from the beginning of loading.

4.2. three points bending

Fig. 6 : Results for 3 points bending on GLARE 2 (0°)

Fig. 7 : Results for 3 points bending on GLARE 2 (45°)

Figure 6 is a comparison between experimental and calculated curves for 3 points bending on GLARE 2 (0°). They are in good agreement.

Figure 7 shows damage evolution at the center of the specimen, for the upper and lower composite layers. We can notice that damage is lower in compression zones, which is in agreement with the model since d' does not change for compression stresses.

4.3. four points bending

Fig.8 : Results for 4 points bending on GLARE 2 (30°)

Figure 8 shows a good agreement between experimental and calculated curves for 4 points bending test on GLARE 2.

CONCLUSION

We have presented a numerical modelling to simulate the behaviour of structures made of laminated plates with isotropic elastic-plastic layers and composite layers with damage.

A Q4g-type plate finite element is used. It is based upon a variational displacement formulation. Transverse shear strains have particular approximation scheme.

Resulting from experimental observations on laminates, the following constitutive laws have been introduced in the numerical model :

- aluminium layers are considered to be elastic-plastic with strain hardening. Their fracture is reached for a critical value of strain.

- composite layers are considered to be elastic with damage. Progressive deterioration is associated to damage variables d and d' which follow linear evolution and represent fibre-matrix decohesion and matrix cracking.

The results that we have obtained are satisfactory. Numerical results for GLARE are determined from identified parameters on material components. Comparisons between experimental and numerical results show that this approach is well fitted for these laminates.

This model, in spite of some limitations, is a numerical tool which permits to simulate the behaviour of metal-composite laminates. It allows to choose the optimal stacking sequence in relation to the behaviour of the material under loading. Some improvements could be provided, for example by taking into account the matrix plasticity within composite plies, or extending plate elements to shell elements.

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